

Metal ion-sensing metalloreceptors that trigger photocrine signaling-based organismal communication

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Understanding how organisms communicate is a fundamental question in biology and is an evolutionarily important milestone. Organisms can communicate via numerous mechanisms including acoustic, gas, and even light-based signaling. Terrestrial organisms largely communicate via gasocrine signaling mediated via gaseous signaling molecules sensed via gas-sensing gasoreceptors. Similar communication principles must also exist in marine organisms and one such mechanism is bioluminescence-mediated communication. However, to the best of my knowledge, there are no specific scientific terms to describe such bioluminescence-mediated organismal communication. I expand photocrine signaling to include light-mediated communication between organisms. Photocrine signaling seems to require metal-ion sensing metalloreceptor proteins such as magnesium-sensing luciferase metalloreceptor and calcium-sensing aequorin metalloreceptor. Similar to luciferase and aequorin metalloreceptors, there must be other metalloreceptors for other metal ions.